

ECONOMIC, DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN IN YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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Introduction

Market relations in our country are not new. The most important task of the first days was to determine the path of our socio-economic development using the rich opportunities and geopolitical conditions of Uzbekistan, where for thousands of years our ancestors traded the wonderful products and natural resources of artisans around the world. The path of reform chosen by Uzbekistan is aimed at building a socially oriented market economy. Based on the principles of transition to a new economic relationship, a very responsible

ABSTRACT

In the article, as we begin to shed light on the radical changes that haven't taken place in our economic life during the years of independence, let us first remember what kind of dependence, Uzbekistan could not own its natural resources, land, water, forests and other resources, and could not determine the path of economic development. During the years of independence, they have developed for the better.

and complex task-economic reform strategy has been developed. The starting point of economic strategy is to set the ultimate goal of socio-economic change. The task is to move from a centralized, command-based economy to market relations, from one quality state to another. traded, exchanged goods.

Material and Methods

According to the market reform program, priorities will be addressed step by step. In the first stage, during the transition from a totalitarian system to the

modern market economy, two interrelated tasks had to be solved simultaneously: overcoming the severe consequences of the command-and-control system, stabilizing the economy and forming the basis of market relations. At this stage, the most important directions of economic reform were identified by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan: - formation of the legal framework for the transition process, strengthening and developing the legal framework for reforms; creation of new forms of ownership in agriculture; - Eliminate the decline in production. The laws and regulations that legally justify economic reforms have been developed by legal organizations and leading scholars and have been endorsed and recognized by

the world's leading experts. Transition to a socially oriented free market economy The main principles of the "Uzbek model" The implementation of the model of modernization and renewal of society, called the "Uzbek model" of development, radically changed the structure of the economy in a historically short time allowed for growth.

Results

Since Uzbekistan gained independence in 1991, the country's GDP has increased almost 4.5 times in terms of purchasing power parity, while in recent years economic growth has been at least 8%.

Discussion

ECONOMIC INTERESTS are the vital needs of the participants of economic activity (economic entities) perceived and motivated by them, the driving force of economic activity.

Individual or individual, depending on the scope of economic interests; group. odor or corporate; is divided into national or national economic interests. The main link in the system of economic interests is the individual interest, which expresses the needs of man as an individual, and because

private interest is primary, its implementation stimulates economic development. A group interest is the general interest of those who are united in a particular community, and within the firm, this interest is based on the burden on the enterprise and the increase of income and profit.

While the profits go to the entrepreneurs, they also involve workers and employees, which means that they are paid bonuses in addition to their salaries. As a result, profit becomes a group interest factor. National

(state) I. m. It is the common economic interest of all nations and peoples living in a given country and is expressed in the quantity and composition of gross domestic product. Sustainable economic growth requires the harmony of economic interests in society.

An important feature of economic interests is the emergence of driving forces behind and the development of business entities. Thus, it reflected the role of the general department of labor and its place in the economic sciences. From this perspective, economic interests will be the goal. They, on the other hand, are always subjective with their carriers.

There is a conscious desire to meet the economic needs of economic needs. This obligation is an objective reason not to engage in economic activity.

For economic entities include groups (groups) of individuals, households, communities and especially individuals. body, economic benefit. This includes services, material goods, information and so on.

Pluralism (complexity) diversifies the economic interests of the needy. They form a complex system, multi-dimensional different production stages, temporary and black cutting.

Organically related concepts such as property and economic interests. In this case, there is a tendency of the economic entity to meet its needs through object ownership and disposal.

Conceal general (group), personal, and social obligations to meet their economic interests and the appropriate needs of their classification disciplines.

Economic interests can be identified by looking at the important and current.

Thus, primary and secondary are separated.

Temporary symptoms of interest may be prospective or current.

According to the objects they can be smart, financial and other property.

According to the level of awareness are divided into imaginary (apparent) and real interests.

They can also be arranged according to utopia and actual implementation options.

Economic agents may express special interests. The general assistance program I ask for to maximize home is in line with available income and prices. , To increase revenue, reduce costs and increase the competitiveness of goods shipped in the interests of entrepreneurs. in their economic activity the state is intended to meet the needs of society as a whole.

classification of economic interests and built in accordance with the territorial principle. Thus, the separation of urban, national, regional aspirations. It can be global (general).

the formation of a country's economic interests is consistent with the distribution of powers between local communities and the government.

Realizing the existing potential in a particular area, the aspiration to meet the specific needs of the regional and local community.

During the complexity of social development and increase, economic systems begin to form a rigid governance. In this case, the situation is complicated by the lack of feedback. In such circumstances, self-interest is a powerful force in socio-economic development, no matter what. subjecting our government intentions contrary to the principles of

operation of complex self-organizing structures. As a result, economic interests are slippery, administrative-command, economic conditions are formed. This place, along with a violation of motivational behavior of subjects, appreciates the need to avoid incentives and reduce the motivational responsibility for high performance. Moreover, in such circumstances, it records the loss of work values and social attitudes. As a result, the psychology of state dependence and (in the economic sense) addiction developed.

There are two ways of competition: competition through price, competition without using price. In times of free competition, the main way to compete was to sell the product at a lower price than the competitor. To use this method, the company must introduce more efficient technology than others, hire more skilled workers and better organize labor. Only in this case, the individual value of its goods is lower than the market value, which allows to reduce the price. The monopolization of the economy is also changing the way we compete. Price-based competition methods are now being replaced by non-price-based methods. In the competition, the importance of product quality, improvement of product sales conditions and advertising is growing.

Since it is impossible for large corporations to squeeze a competitor out of the market without lowering prices, they reduce the supply of goods by reducing the use of their production capacity to change the situation in the market. Therefore, even in times of crisis, prices will remain stable.

Priceless competition is important even where there are monopolies, because:

1) Reducing the price does not allow to increase the sale of goods, because the competitor can also reduce the price, and no one wins. Thus, the transition to improving the quality of goods, improving sales services, thereby increasing sales of goods;

2) Because large firms are strong, they can spend a lot of money on product upgrades, modernization, and advertising.

The use of non-price competition does not mean that price is not used in competition. It is becoming more secretive, meaning that goods are sold for less than the advertised price, and others are not notified. This is especially true when selling seasonal goods. Price-based competition has also entered the world market. There, price competition is common in the steel, fabric, electronics, chemical, and agricultural markets. 3. The concept of elasticity, in which demand and supply change according to prices, is used.

This understanding helps us to better understand the process of market adaptation to changes in the key factors that determine the dynamics of supply and demand.

Demand and supply of different goods will vary depending on price changes. An increase in the price of a primary commodity may not affect the level of demand.

For example, the prices of bread, butter, sugar, and potatoes increase, but the demand for them does not change. But demand for related products may change. People are consuming less white bread and more black bread.

This will lead to a decline in the living standards of people, the main goal of

society, and a decline in normal consumption.

An increase in the price of secondary products often leads to a decrease in demand for them. For example: carpets, jewelry, cars, etc. It should be noted that the increase in prices for primary products has little effect on the volume of demand, so the enterprises producing primary products will quickly emerge from the crisis.

In the material sectors, which produce secondary products, production crises will last a long time.

Therefore, the total revenue of the seller is equal to the value obtained by multiplying

the price of the goods by the sum of the value of the total volume of goods.

Conclusion

In short, the stability of our economic, socio-political, cultural and educational work in building a democratic society based on market relations in Uzbekistan makes it an important task to prevent ideological threats. To this end, based on the traditions, customs, language, religion, psyche of our people, it is necessary to instill in the minds of people feelings of confidence in the future, compassion, honesty, patience, justice and enlightenment.

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